

WIDOWHOOD RITES: EXPERIENCES AND PERCEPTIONS AMONG THE IBIBIO PEOPLE OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

The study which is purely a qualitative enquiry was designed to examine widowhood rites: experiences and perceptions among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State. Three specific objectives were set out by the researchers and they adopted the descriptive ethnographic method in carrying out this investigation. Four different Local Government Areas and three communities from each of the LGA were studied. It is an indisputable fact that discrimination against and abuse of widows of all ages occurs across a wide spectrum of cultures, religions, ethnic groups, and regions, irrespective of the economic or educational status of these widows, they are still subjected to this oppression, and Ibibio ethnic group of Akwa Ibom State is not left out. In some communities in Ibibio land, widows are coerced into participating in harmful, degrading and even life-threatening traditional practices as part of burial and mourning rites. Attitudes to, and treatment of widows vary among the various communities studied. However, one common phenomenon discovered was that widows in these areas undergo diverse inhumane treatment. The dehumanizing effects of these treatments have resulted in the impoverishment of most of these widows as their livelihoods are usually taken away and this makes the women go through different challenges such as; emotional and psychological trauma, physical abuse and severe obnoxious treatment. Against this backdrop, the study recommends a public enlightenment campaign to educate people about the harmful effects of evil widowhood rites practices. These could be in the form of television and radio jingles in the local dialect of the people, for those in the rural areas to be aware and well informed

Keywords: widow, widowhood experiences, perceptions of widowhood, widowhood rites

Introduction

Over the years, harmful traditional widowhood rites have been one of the major challenges faced by women daily across most African societies, most especially in Nigeria and particularly in Ibibio communities. Widowhood in other parts of the world is not as challenging as it is in African societies. In Africa, the experience of widowhood can be quite devastating and disheartening to the woman who has just lost her husband, more so, in a patriarchal society like Nigeria. Widowhood rites are one of the practices that undermines the rights and well-being of African women among other practices such as; early marriages and

female Genital Mutilation (FGM), even in a time like this when the world has set out to achieve goal five of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) of Gender equality and empowerment of all women and girls by 2030. According to Layi (2000), African women remain victims of harmful rites that are associated with the passing away of their beloved spouses. Deaths even in circumstances in which the causes are natural and explicable, are never perceived as such in African communities. Deaths are attributed to other factors and widows are targets of accusations about bewitchment or sorcery and are as such blamed for the deaths of their beloved partners.

Brown (1992) also stressed that in most African communities the death of a spouse is seen as a serious matter, which involves all observances of a series of rituals and ceremonies, all meant to signify the separation of the deceased spouse spiritually from the surviving ones. This is based on the general belief that the relationship between the spouse is a special one and that something must be done to mark the permanent severance of the relationship and the departure of one of the partners. Okolo (1997), in explaining the experience that accompanies the loss of a spouse, posited that it is widely known in folklore that although all enduring marriages ultimately end with the death of either the husband or the wife or both, the disorganizing or traumatic experience which accompanies the death of the husband tends to be greater than that which accompanies the death of a wife. Two main reasons are given for this; widows are subjected to a variety of arduous and degrading rites and secondly, widows are usually seen as inferior to men usually, by lack of means of sustaining themselves and their children.

In most West African countries, widowhood is determined by cohabitation, customary marriage or marriage of ordinance. The marriage of ordinance refers to Western type of monogamous or marriage in a magistrate court, in a church, or according to Islamic laws. By cohabitation, a woman could live with a man for many years without getting married either customarily or legally. This union could result in having children or no children but upon the death of the man, the woman is expected to perform widowhood rites even though she may not be recognized as a “proper wife”. The loss of a spouse is one of the most negative life events next only to the loss of a child (Fasoranti and Aruna, 2007). Conversely, in Ibibio communities, Ekanem (2015) explains that a widow in traditional Ibibio society was a woman who had been legitimately married through customary laws, but who had lost her husband through death. Legitimate traditional marriage was an important factor in widowhood, because according to Ibibio customary laws, a man who cohabited with a woman without performing the traditional marriage rites could not be ritually mourned by his partner if he died. This is contrary to what Fasoranti and Aruna, (2007) opined to be obtainable in other African societies where a woman who cohabits with a man in a union can be involved in widowhood rites upon the death of a man, even when they were never married either customarily or legally.

Whatever the case may be one fact that stands out is that daily widows go through harmful traditional widowhood rites that infringe upon their fundamental human rights and other abounding adverse consequences in Ibibio communities. It was against this backdrop that this study was conducted to the experiences and perceptions of widowhood rites among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of this study were to;

1. Investigate the experiences of widows as regards widowhood rites among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
2. Examine the problems associated with widowhood rites among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
3. Determine measures to mitigate the challenges faced by widows as a result of the passing away of their husbands in Ibibio among the Ibibio people of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria.

Literature Review

Perceptions of widows and widowhood rites

Available works of literature suggest that widows are severally affected financially, psychologically and socially (Stallion, 1984). However, the experiences of widows differ among ethnic groups, nations, social class and religious groups. These factors notwithstanding, all widows are affected by the loss of their husbands. In Ibibio communities for instance, after the death of a man has been made public through announcement by the appropriate authority, the wife/wives had to wail in order to attract the neighbors to the compound. As accounted for by Ekanem (2015) it was mandatory for women especially the widows to wail and cry otherwise it would be considered obnoxious to customary etiquette and a sign of complicity in the death. Other women, who were attracted to the compound of the bereaved through wailing, could take part in the wailing as a sign of solidarity and empathy for the bereaved family. Men were also attracted to the compound of the bereaved but would rather be in sober moods, separately from the women without shedding tears as such public display or “feminine” emotion was considered infra dig to manliness and culturally obnoxious (Ekanem, 2002). He further explained that following this, was a daily routine from the death was announced to the day of the funeral rite. The mourning wife/wives along with other women from the extended family would remain in the corpse and from time to time massage it from becoming stiff before the funeral. And at the funeral rites the wife/wives are wail and cry as aloud as possible so as to demonstrate that they were really touched by the death, any of them that treated the entire exercise of mourning and crying with levity would be suspected of complicity in the death (Ekanem, 2002).

In other Nigerian societies like the Igbo culture Afigbo (1989) highlighted that it is the moment death arrives that tumult begins. There is an outburst of wailing. Sometimes a wife will rush from the home heedless of direction, waving the arms, and beating her breast as she bemoans her loss at the top of her voice. This type of bitter wailing is expected to go on until the remains of the man have been buried. Even after that, the wife/wives is/are expected to enact a wail or two every morning between the hours of 5.am or 6.am forwards of four days or more. Odimegwu (2002) gives a detailed account of widowhood rites and experience among the Igbo in Anambra and Imo state. He explained that widows in these areas are subjected to certain rites in accordance with the custom and tradition of the people. In other areas of Imo state, he noted that the moment a woman lost her husband, she must leave her air open and in bad condition. She is not allowed to sleep on a bed but on a mat. She is given a machete with which to fight evil spirit every morning for one month. One of the sisters-in-law takes her out to cry aloud. She is not allowed to eat with the children as it is believed that it bring them

sickness or death. She is confined for four weeks where is suspected or believe that she did not live in harmony with her partner during his life time. After this stage, and the burial she wears black clothing for one whole year. Now she can go to farm and markets. During the mourning periods she must not intercourse with any man and must she show respect to her husband's relatives.

In Oweri area, he accounts that the widow is expected to shout and scream in tears on the death of her husband. The hair is left loose. Her first meal after the death of her husband has to eaten from a broken dirty pot/plate, and not before her hands is washed in a traditional way by another widow. When the deceased is not buried, she is expected to sit in a place and moved out accompanied only to ease herself. He further explained that in Abor-Mbaise, the widow is expected to sit on a bare floor screaming until she is tired. If she is pregnant she will stop wearing black at the end of the 8th month of her pregnancy. Tradition stipulates she should not deliver her baby while still wearing black. The widow should not wear ear rings or makeup. She is not expected to attend festivities, but she can attend burial ceremonies. However, the rites are not the same across social status in the community. The widow is expected to cry three times daily 5.30am, 12.00am and before bed time. In Amigbo community of Orlu area in Imo state during the mourning period she may not be allowed to go out only under certain exigencies. The widow is confine for six months if the deceased is a title man and three months in the case of a non-title holder (Odimegwu, 2000). According to him widows regard the rites as necessary to prove the love their deceased spouse or to establish their innocence in the case of deaths of their husband. Others perceived the rites as cultural imperatives that must be adhered to, else severe penalty. Punishment or penalty awaits any widow who does not observe these rites. This treatment to a great extent depends on the widow's relationship with family members.

Widows' experiences

As explained by Ewelukwa, Onyema and Ewelukwa, (2019), the experience of widows across different cultures are heavily influenced by deeply ingrained attitudes, norms and practices that perpetuates discrimination and exacerbate their vulnerability. In a study carried out by Makama on: “patriarchy and gender inequality in Nigeria: The way forward” he explained the experiences faced by widows in Nigeria to include; customary norm that enforce practice like isolation, forced hair shaving, accusation of marital foul play and denial of inheritance rights (Makama, 2019). Other negative experiences of widows include; physical or sexual violence with forced marriage bring pervasive, coercing widows into union against their will, either with relative or strangers. As it is reported by International Centre for Research on Women (ICRN), 38% of widows in Nigeria reported different forms of abuses against them. The dehumanizing rituals that further strip widows of their dignity perpetuating their vulnerability in society. This vulnerability is compounded by discrimination, social exclusion, and limited access to resources or exacerbated by prevalent gender based violence (GBV) and encompassing physical, sexual, psychological and financial abuse (ICRN, 2016). A particular study shown that as high as 63% of widows experience clinical depression as against 15% prevalence among married couples which goes further to indicate the debilitating effects of widowhood experiences (Onasoga, Afolayan and Oladimeji, 2019). Widows experiencing feelings of sadness, worthlessness, fatigue, sleep disturbance and suicidal ideation, further complicated by limited access to counselling services or support groups to assist in the grieving process (Agu, *et al.*, 2022).

According to Samuel and Tawosa, (2019), the social isolation and stigmatization that widows endure exacerbate their mental health, difficulties, while financial struggle and unmet basic needs significantly contribute to heightened levels of anxiety and stress.

Theoretical Framework

Cultural Conflict Theory

Cultural conflict, as articulated by Jonathan H. Turner in 2005, refers to disputes arising from "differences in cultural values and beliefs that place people at odds with one another." Such conflicts are particularly challenging to resolve due to the divergent beliefs held by the involved parties. The intensity of cultural conflicts often escalates when these differences manifest in political arenas, especially on a macro scale. A pertinent illustration of cultural conflict is the ongoing debate surrounding abortion, while ethnic cleansing serves as a more extreme manifestation of such discord. In the context of this study, cultural conflict is relevant to the experiences of widows, particularly concerning the treatment of some widows in Africa, and specifically in Nigeria. Among the Ibibio community in Akwa Ibom State, the experiences of widows have highlighted a significant cultural conflict within their practices. The cultural dimensions have led to serious conflicts with various norms and values that are integral to the cultural identity of the Ibibio people.

Methodology

Ibibio people presently occupy 14 out of the 31 Local Government areas of Akwa Ibom State, which forms the majority ethnic group. Akwa Ibom state lies between latitude "4⁰25 and 5⁰30" North and longitude "7⁰30 and 8⁰30" East. The state is bounded in the North by Cross River state and by the Bight of Bonny in the South. In the West, it shares a common boundary with Abia state. Ibibio land lies within the vegetation belt of tropical rain forest (Esema, 2002).

The study was designed as a descriptive ethnography relying exclusively and purely on qualitative methods. The individual in the communities serve as the basis of data collection and interpretation. A total of three focus group discussions and 6 in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants who were selected purposively. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select four three government areas. For the focus group discussions, the participants were widows, some who have been victims of harmful traditional widowhood rites, opinion leaders (including chiefs and family heads). The in-depth interviews were conducted with six women who have been victims of harmful widowhood rites. The numbers of the in-depth interview participants were determined by saturation of ideas.

Open-ended unstructured and flexible discussion guide was prepared to collect data. The discussion guide to identify the experiences and perceptions of widowhood practices among the Ibibio and challenges pose by these widowhood rites was prepared.

One research expert was recruited to facilitate the focus group discussions and the co-researchers also assisted the principal researcher. The principal investigator was responsible for conducting the in-depth interviews and moderating the FGDs. Both FGDs and in-depth interviews were tape recorded, and notes were taken simultaneously. The FGD took 45 to 60 minutes, whereas the in-depth interview lasted about 45 minutes. The interview was

conducted using study participants' local language (Ibibio). Audio taped data and the detailed notes were transcribed and translated into English.

Findings

Widowhood rites in Uyo

The widowhood rites among the Ibibio vary according to locality whether urban/rural, or religion, whether Christianity or African traditional religion. Moreover, they also vary according to families and wealth of the deceased man. The only common widowhood rites still very much practice in Akwa Ibom is the customary law that prevents widows from inheriting directly from their husbands' landed and personal property which are usually inherited by the husband's relations, in the case where there is no male child.

Most widows in Uyo metropolis, a typical urban setting, complained of being dispossessed of their husband's property, thus leaving their young children in dire want. As a result, their children drop out of school to work as domestic servants or become destitute.

Moreover, a widow that is suspected of causing the death of her husband is required to swear an oath and/or drink the water, which has been used to wash the corpse of the deceased. Other rites like being confined to place for a period of time, or shaving her hair, being inherited as a chattel by her husband's brothers are no longer practiced in the urban areas.

Ikot Eboro Ikono (a rural area in Uyo Local Government)

The above rural village is also an Ibibio community. A widow is forced to swear to an oath to absolve her of being responsible for the death of her husband or to allow the relation of her deceased husband to gain access of his wealth. Moreover, widows are required to take oath as proof that they would truthfully declare all the asset of their spouse. Widows who fail to cooperate may be severely beaten to the point of death except by timely intervention of the police. This normally leads to the seizure of the deceased property. Corpse may be abandoned to a widow and her family for burial if she is uncooperative.

Widowhood rites in Ikono Local Government Area

In Ikono Local Government Area, still an Ibibio community, a Christian burial is given where the deceased is a Christian. There is no dress code or restriction for Christian widows. Mourning is a personal choice of the widow. However, his kin dispossesses some widows of their husband's property. This is done whether or not the widow has children for the late husband. It would be worse if there are no children or if all of them are female. A discussant during the focus group discussion observed that even if the widow has twelve daughters, none of them could inherit anything from their late fathers' property since the inheritance pattern is strictly patrilineal.

My sister has five female children. When the husband died, she was told by the husband's brothers that since she did not give birth to any male child, she and the female children did not have right to it.

There was also the case of an elderly woman whose husband died recently. It was claimed that the husband's next of kin seized the entire property of her late husband and sent her out of the house. She attempted suicide as a result.

When my husband died, my husband's younger brother who was his next of kin came in and claimed that the house and other property belong to him since he was the next of kin to my late husband. We had to manage with one of my sister's house. I almost killed myself, but because of my children I managed to survive.

Widowhood rites in Uruan Local Government Area

A widow is always a suspect here as far as her husband's death is concern. She must swear to an oath to prove her innocence. An older widow who would summon, and confine her to a room, where she is forced to sit on the floor as long as the dead is not buried. Shaving of her hair including the pubic hair follows. She pays an amount of money and some bottles of drink for this ritual. Her movement is restricted for a period of a year. She is not allowed to cut her nail, take her bath, sing, talk or go to the market during this period. She may be allowed to take her bath during her menstrual period, but under supervision by older widows who will lead her back to confinement. The old widow would now permit her to change or remove the mourning clothe after the period of mourning. However, the new dress, which is black, is worn for a month these days unlike in the past when it was for a year.

Shaving and cutting of her nails follows this. These items are burnt, signaling complete separation with the dead. The next stage is to choose a husband for her from within the extended family of the dead husband. Having made this choice, she is mandated to offer the old widow an amount of money and food is prepared for the group with some specified number of kegs of palm wine, fowl, and other items as demanded by them.

These items are then presented to the men of the family who would now approach the selected new husband. He is then duly informed that he has been chosen to be the widow's next husband. If, however, he rejects the offer, the widow is again made to choose another man who is also from the same family. The man is required on acceptance, to buy for the new wife (i.e., widow) clothes, tubers of yam and other items as demanded by the custom of the people.

Kin hesitate to inherit widows because of the harsh economic conditions. In most cases, older widows now choose one of the sons (i.e., the first son) which are also acceptable. The researcher noticed many young widows in this village; some have been disposed of their husbands' properties and are now in their parents' home, while others were left to take care of their children single-handedly after the deceased property had been sold out under the pretext of using the money to give their "brother" a befitting burial.

Moreover, it is a taboo for the widow to marry outside the family of the dead husband in this area. Death, through the diabolical means, is the penalty for any widow who marries outside the family. Widows are still inherited in another village in the local government. The property of her deceased spouse would be seized. If they refused to comply, they are attacked spiritually. The village chairman in his contribution during the Focused Group Discussion argued that it is their custom and it must be sustained. Widows indicated that they had no choice but to comply since it is their custom.

Children suffered most because they are not well cared for by inheritors. The inheritors visit them occasionally; give them a very small amount of money that cannot sustain them and their children. Wife inheritance in this village these days is just to meet the sexual need of man and their reproductive desire. The first son of the inherited widow interviewed dropped out of school because of lack of a good father figure to discipline him. The widows and their children detest the custom of inheritance.

Widowhood rites in Ikono Local Government Area

In Ikot Ide Itak, a rural village in Ikono Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, in an in-depth interview with an old widow, the interview reveals that in the community when

a husband dies, the widow is not expected to comb her hair, nor cut the hair. The hair is left scattered and unkept “idet akpe”. She was not also expected to take her bath, as well as being prevented from going out, until the fulfillment of the specified period of time. Throughout this period, she puts on dirty clothes without shoes, usually for three months. All through this period she is expected to be in the house crying without going out.

After the last ritual, called 'usuan ufok ikpo' that is, dissolution of the funeral committee. A last meeting is convened by the family head, where the widow is to choose a male from the husband brother or cousins to marry, who would be responsible for taking care of her and the children as well as inheriting the husband's property. However, in a case where she refused to choose from any of the husband's brothers and cousins, she was to remain for the children and was not expected to marry anyone. If she defies the order of the elders, and remarries outside the family, there was serious punishment that could be meted against her; such punishment may include denial of inheritance right. This means that she could not partake in anything that belongs to the late husband and she could also be banished from the community.

During our time in the past, when our husband died, we were not expected to comb our hair, nor cut the hair. The hair is left scattered and unkempt this is called “idet akpe”. we were not also expected to take our bath, as well as being prevented from going out, until the fulfillment of the specified period of time. Throughout this period, we used to put on dirty clothes without shoes, usually for three months. All through this period we were expected to be in the house crying without going out. After the last ritual, called 'usuan ufok ikpo', a last meeting is convened by the family head, where we were asked to choose a male from among our late husband brothers or cousins to be married to, who would be responsible for taking care of us and the children, as well as inheriting our late husband's property. However, in a case where any of us refused to choose from any of the husband's brothers and cousins, we were to remain for our children and not expected to marry anyone. If anyone defies the order of the elders, and remarries outside the family, there was serious punishment that could be meted against her; such punishment used to include denial of inheritance right. This means that she could not partake in anything that belongs to the late husband and she could also be banished from the community.

She added that this practice was not the same across socio-religious lines. She further explains that a widow to a traditionalist and a Christian widow didn't go through the same widowhood rites. For instance in the case of a Christen family, after the funeral ceremony the entire family and other well-wishers will accompany the woman to church for prayers.

As regards drinking water used in bathing the corpse of the deceased husband in the community; another widow had this to say:

When a widow is accused of killing the husband, the practice of given the widow the water used in washing the corpse of the late husband was invoked against the widow in order to prove that she was innocent. If she drinks the water after some incantations must have been made and she survives, she would be made to remove her black cloth, but if she was guilty she could not

survive.

Another participant narrated that;

Now when a husband dies, a widow is expected to invite the entire socio-cultural group she belongs, to stage a ballad and cultural dance in honor and memory of her late husband. The occasion is also used as an avenue to raise a token in support of the widow. Likewise, such practice such as long period of mourning has become outdated. Instead of long period of mourning and sorrow, widows are at liberty to cry or not to cry and after a few days she goes about her normal duties. Things have changed, not as in the olden days.

All the women however maintained that this type of tradition has become obsolete due to factors such as: the spread of Christianity, better understanding, western education and modernization. She further explains that in the present day the rites that widows perform is rather such rites and rituals that serves as marks of respect, love and honor to the late husband, for instance, as part of series of events to mark the funeral ritual.

Discussion of Findings

In the findings of the study, it was discovered that though the experiences of widows across the four local government areas that the study considered are not the same, but differ according to a number of factors. These experiences can be said to be relative to places, family and prevailing religious belief of the people or the deceased husband. One common adverse effect of this practice is the degrading and dehumanizing effects of customary law practices of widowhood. There are other effects that include: enforced persistent wailing. This practice is physically debilitating and disruptive. As a result of crying and rolling on the ground, many suffer physical symptoms like insomnia, shortness of breath and loss of appetite. Physical health problems associated with widowhood practices are embodiment of untidiness, hunger and starvation, brutality and physical pains.

Other negative impact of this harmful widowhood practice is the severe implications it has on the whole society. Specifically the impoverished status of widows does not only affect them, but also deprive their children of human rights to shelter, food, education and the rights of the child. The long term negative implications of these practices on the society are huge.

Recommendations

Since clear evidence from the field work has shown that widows in Ibibio communities undergo diverse inhumane treatment, and the dehumanizing effects of these treatment have resulted in the impoverishment of most of these widows as their livelihood are usually taken away and this makes the women to go through different challenges such as emotional and psychological trauma, physical abuse and severe obnoxious treatment, also considering that has been done in the past in these communities to placate these widows, hence, considering the above conclusion; the following recommendations are paramount in pacifying the plights of widows:

- I. There should be public enlightenment campaign to educate the people about the harmful effects of evil widowhood rites practices. These could be in form of television and radio jingles in the local dialect of the people, in order for those in the

- rural areas to be aware and well informed
- II. Workshops, seminars, posters, handbills and health talk in the local dialect should also be embarked upon by relevant bodies.
 - III. Traditional rulers, such as village heads, clan heads and paramount rulers, opinion leaders, traditional birth attendants, religious leaders and key figures in the communities whose opinion are highly respected should also be trained and educated on the harmful effects of these widowhood rites that undermines the rights and dignities of these widows.
 - IV. Laws should be enacted that prohibit these barbaric cultures and traditions that subjugate and discriminate against the women folks.
 - V. Government at all levels; federal, state and local government councils Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and philanthropists, should provide funds to support the widows who are victims of harmful traditional widowhood rites in these communities.

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